

Event Abstract

Knowledge & Health Beliefs toward Cervical Cancer Screening & Prevention among Libyan females attending Gynaecology & Obstetric out-patient clinic at Tripoli Medical Centre (2010)

Fozia Kemishi ^{1*}

¹ Albadri polyclinic, Tripoli, Libya.

² Department of Obstetrics & Gynecology, Faculty of Medicine, Tripoli University, Tripoli, Libya.

³ Airport Road polyclinic, Tripoli, Libya.

Background: Cancer cervix is highly preventable disease through screening. Aims: to explore knowledge, attitude and practices of Libyan women toward cervical cancer screening and prevention.

Methods: A sample of 316 patients was chosen randomly from patients attending the Gynae-obstetric out-patient clinic in TMC .survey was conducted via a self-administered and anonymous questionnaire which was of closed ended questions, and included: socio-demographic data , general knowledge about cervical cancer and Pap smear tests, reasons of having / not having a smear test in the past, awareness of HPV vaccine as a preventive tool and willing to receive the vaccine if it would become available. Data was analysed using SPSS (version11).

Results: 59.2% of women were aware of Pap smear. Regarding the risk factors, women were aware about were: HPV in 50%, multiple sexual partners in 54%, illegitimate sexual relations in 51%, the use of OCP for more than five years in 65%, and smoking in 86%. 75.9% of participants knew that Pap smear can diagnose cervical precancerous lesions and 91.1% of them believed that cancer cervix is curable if diagnosed early. Regarding cervical cancer screening status: only 6% were screened. 57.9% had PAP smear advised by doctors while 42.1% had it because of cervical pathology. Regarding HPV vaccine only 28.2% are aware of it while 87% of women are willing to receive it.

Conclusion: The current situation in Libya, based on opportunistic screening is not effective in reaching the

majority of the population. Awareness of and willing to receive HPV vaccine is very low.

Keywords: Libya, Cancer cervix, screening and HPV vaccine.

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* **Correspondence:** Dr. Fozia Kemishi, Albadri polyclinic, Tripoli, Libya, foziakemishi@hotmail.com